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Understanding Spanish financial crises severity, 1850-2015*

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Abstract

Although many factors impinge upon financial crises, their depth and macroeconomic impact have varied throughout history. What might explain the reasons for these differences? This paper examines the main factors behind the severity of Spanish financial crises over the last 165 years. We complete an in-depth analysis of all types of crises (banking, currency, stock market and debt) considering a long term series of external imbalances (with an estimation of the current account balance for the period 1914-1930). Using modern methods of statistical analysis (local projections), we find that current account is a key variable in determining the severity of Spain's financial crises.

Key words: Spain, financial history, financial crises, current account, credit growth

JEL code: N20, G01, N10, F32, E51

1. Introduction

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Although there are many factors involved in financial crises, their depth and macroeconomic impact have varied throughout history. Most crises are related to changes in regulation, financial innovations, booms of assets, bad practices, scandals and corruption, and so on. However, there are also differences in the type of crises. In general, severity is higher when more than one type of crisis occurs at the same time. So, banking crises that are also accompanied by currency and stock market crises (even sovereign default) tend to be more severe (Reinhart and Rogoff 2009). However, even in the case of these combinations, there are also differences in magnitude and exceptions. What might be the reasons for these differences in terms of severity?

A large amount of literature has been generated regarding the factors that led to the current financial crisis with most recent debate focusing on the role of current account imbalances and credit booms. However, empirical research in this debate mainly considers a short period of time, near to more recent crises. A longer period was contemplated in Bordo et al (2001), Bordo, Meissner and Stuckler (2006) and Bordo and Meissner (2011) using a database for two globalization periods: 1880-1913, for 18 countries, and 1973-2003, with 45 countries. The results tend towards the external imbalance hypothesis. A long dataset for 140 years, 1870-2008, and a sample of 14 advanced countries is used in Jordà, Schularick and Taylor (2011, 2013, 2016), Taylor (2012a,b) and Schularick and Taylor (2012). The authors argue that the key determinant of financial crises is in fact credit growth, especially after 1945. As mentioned in Bordo and Meissner (2016), these different results may be explained by a number of factors. First, different studies consider different types of crises. Thus, for example, Jordà, Schularick and Taylor (2011, 2013) only count banking crises, while Bordo et al (2001) take into account currency and banking crises. Second, different crisis dates have been used, following the research of other economic historians. Third, the particular samples of countries are quite diverse, ranging from more advanced countries to the less developed. Moreover, most of this research in fact attempts to predict crises. Indeed, few studies contemplate

the severity of crises (with some few exceptions, such as Jordà, Schularick and Taylor (2013, 2016) or Rose and Spiegel (2011) for the 2008 crisis).

This paper contributes to this general discussion by examining the experience of Spain over a period of 165 years (1850-2015). A single country analysis enables us to use the best data available along with other contemporary sources. Consequently, we can complete an in-depth analysis of every single crisis that has occurred in Spain over this long timeframe. Furthermore, Spain is an interesting case study for several reasons. Firstly, during most of the considered period Spain was an agrarian and less developed country, with a small capital market and a weak financial system. The studies that concentrate on the “credit hypothesis”, such as Jordà, Schularick and Taylor (2011, 2013, 2016), Taylor (2012a,b) or Schularick and Taylor (2012), mainly consider advanced countries. However, although the transmission mechanism from credit expansion to financial crisis could work in financially developed countries, where credit plays a crucial role in the economy, the result could be different for less developed countries with an immature financial system and a relatively scarce use of credit. In fact, the analysis of the literature shows that the importance of credit was relatively low. However, external imbalance is a recurrent factor in the explanation of Spanish financial instability. Therefore, the current account hypothesis appears to be the most probable factor behind greater crisis severity and the aim of this paper is to contrast our approach with previous studies.

Secondly, in Spain crisis severity exhibits a different pattern to that of other countries: post-1973 crises were more severe than in many other countries, with an average cumulative GDP loss of 16.3 per cent (up to 25.97 per cent in 1976 and 27.33 per cent in 2008). This impact is of 14.3 per cent, almost double that of the world average of 8.3 per cent when comparing the period 1973-2000¹. However, interwar crises, including the 1931 depression, were less severe in Spain with a crisis severity of only 4.12 per cent, an impact three times smaller than the world average of 13.4

¹ Data for the world average from 1973 to 1997 came from Bordo et al (2001).

per cent (Betrán, Martín-Aceña and Pons 2012 for Spain and Bordo et al. 2001 for the world average). As we will try to show in this paper, this pattern could be related to the evolution of external imbalances: high current account deficits explain the high severity of the 1976, 1982 and 2008 crises, whereas relatively lower current account deficits are behind the comparatively lower (by international standards) severity of the 1931 crisis².

Spain has also another interesting singularity. As mentioned, most crises were multiple, where triple crises (in currency, banking and stock market) were the deepest, and at times these even coincided in several cases with a fiscal or debt crisis. Bordo and Meisser (2016) affirm that fiscal and financial crises have coincided in history but especially after WWII, when government authorities intervened after banking crises to rescue banks in difficulties, increasing public deficit. However, in Spain during the nineteenth century, banking, currency and debt crises concurred even before governments intervened to fiscally resolve banking crises. For this reason, in this paper we consider currency, banking, stock market and debt crises, as well as possible combinations of these. This is also a difference between this paper and the existing literature on financial crises. As Bordo and Eichengreen (1999), Bordo and Meissner (2011, 2016), or Reinhart and Rogoff (2009) remark interconnections between types of crises have a long history. Besides, the most recent approaches on the theoretical literature on financial and fiscal crises often combine banking and fiscal crises with currency crises. The variety of crises in the Spanish case could help us to contrast whether multiple crises are more severe than a single crisis.

The paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we define crisis severity and present a brief narrative of the main Spanish financial crises to find empirical hypotheses behind the economic drivers of financial crisis severity. As there is no data available for current account for the period 1914 to 1930, we have had to make a crude construction of the current account balance to better

² Moreover, Spain never adopted the gold standard and as Eichengreen and Irwin (2010) stated for the 1929 crisis, those countries that abandoned the gold standard, allowing their currencies to depreciate, had a lower crisis severity because they saw their balance of payments strengthened and benefited from gold inflows.

understand Spain's international position for these years. In Section 3, using Local Projections methods (LP) (Jordá, Schularick and Taylor 2013) and considering current account as our treatment variable and including several controls, we obtain that there is a close relationship between external imbalances and the severity of financial recessions. Moreover, we have also applied the methodology of Jordá, Schularick and Taylor (2016), which addresses potential problems of endogeneity by estimating LP using inverse propensity-score weighting regression adjustment (IPWRA). This estimate confirms that current account imbalances are associated with deeper financial recessions. The main conclusions are offered in Section 4.

2. What determined Spanish financial crises? A long run consideration

As mentioned above, there are interconnections among different types of crises. In general, banking crises are closely related to the inherent characteristics of financial institutions (Bordo 1998) and are typically linked to flawed risk evaluation, problems of risk concentration, credit booms or bad banking practices. By contrast, currency crises are more correlated with the exchange rate regime and current account imbalances. However, third-generation models connect currency crisis (first and second generation) models with banking crisis models³ and show a pattern of crisis transmission from banking to currency crises. Although banking crises often precede currency crises, currency problems deepen banking difficulties and a vicious spiral between both types of crises is activated.

There is also a combined incidence of fiscal and financial crises. The linkages between banking and debt crashes have a two-way direction. Banking crises can lead to debt crises when the government bails out insolvent banks and the increase in sovereign debt becomes unsustainable (Bordo and Meissner 2016). In a similar fashion, debt crises could contribute to a banking crisis when banks hold a significant amount of public debt (Reinhart and Rogoff 2011). Debt crises could

³ See Kaminsky and Reinhart (1999) or Chang and Velasco (2001), among others.

also influence currency crises when deficits are financed with an expansion of money, causing a currency crisis, as happened in nineteenth century Spain.

Finally, banking and stock market crashes are also related⁴. Easy bank credit could lead to asset price booms (Bordo and Landon Lane 2013). When the stock market falls, there is a loss of confidence, economic activity slows down and banks are often hit by this downturn. The situation could worsen when banks have a considerable portfolio. Stock market crashes and debt crises could also be related when most of the assets that are commercialised in the stock market are public debt. This is the case of Spain, where banks had a considerable industrial portfolio and they were strongly involved in the financing of the public deficit and had important amounts of public debt in their assets (Comín and Cuevas 2017). Taking into account these interconnections we maintain that the consideration of currency, banking, stock market and debt crises could enrich the analysis of the severity of a crisis.

Between 1850 and 2015 Spain had to endure nineteen financial crises of diverse types and different depths and durations (see Tables 1 and Appendix 1 for definitions of different types of crises)⁵. Most financial literature uses a function of GDP growth to measure the depth of a financial crisis. Normally, the depth is the cumulative loss of output, estimated by summing the differences between trend growth before the crisis and output growth until annual output growth has returned to its pre-crisis trend. Trend growth is estimated using the average growth for periods delimited by two peak years (Prados 2003). Duration is defined as the number of years until GDP growth returns to its pre-crisis trend.

According to Appendix 2, using the output loss measure in Spain the most severe crisis was in 2008 (27.33 per cent from 2008 to 2013)⁶ followed by 1976 (25.97 per cent). The period 1973-

⁴ In fact, all Spanish stock market crises were multiple with the exception of the 1905 crisis.

⁵ In some cases, allocating a specific year to a crisis could be difficult. For multiple crises we have chosen a year as a representative of the different crises, following Bordo et al (2001).

⁶ We have estimated an output loss for the 2008 crisis of 27.33 per cent assuming that the crisis ended in 2013. The annual rate of GDP growth was once again positive in 2014 (2.2 per cent in the last quarter) but

2015 was the worst, with an average output loss of 16.93 per cent, which contrasts with the results for the world average obtained by Bordo et al (2001) where both the interwar period and the 1929-31 crisis were the deepest. However, in Spain the 1929 Great Depression had a relatively lower impact than in other countries. The ranking (in brackets) of Spanish crises in terms of the largest output loss is as follows: 1866 (6), 1882 (4), 1931 (5), 1976 (2), 1982 (3) and 2008 (1), Triple crises (banking, currency and stock market crises simultaneously) were recorded in 1882, 1931, 1976 and 2008⁷. By types of crises, the most severe are triple or double crises that also coincided with a debt crisis (such as the 1882, 1976 or 2008 crises), confirming that multiple crises are the most severe.

Appendix 2 shows our study includes some crises that are not considered for Spain by the main database used by Bordo et al (2001), Jordà et al (2011) and Reinhart and Rogoff (2010). We obtain the following results. Firstly, our long-term analysis starts in 1850 and consequently we include the 1855 and 1866 crises. Secondly, it identifies certain crises that are not in cross-country studies (1874, 1899, 1905, 1943 and 1948), some of them very severe (mainly the 1866 and 1874 crises) and considered in the literature⁸.

Appendix 2 indicates that, especially in the nineteenth century, most financial crises coincided with periods of debt crises. Debt crises include some debt defaults (1871, 1876)⁹, some debt restructuring (1867, 1881, 1900) and two IMF interventions (1959/60, 1978) (Comín 2012 and Reinhart and Rogoff 2010).

Table 1 and Appendix 2 and 3 describe the main characteristics of Spanish financial crises and this analysis allows us to argue that current account deficits played an important role in the

below the pre-crisis growth rate -that rate was reached in the second quarter of 2015. Spain returned to its previous GDP levels in 2016. Thus, this estimation is a low bound.

⁷ The 1882 and 1976 triple crises also coincided with a debt crisis. The 2008 crisis was mainly a banking crisis but with rapid deterioration in the Spanish fiscal position (Betrán and Pons 2017).

⁸ The 1866 crisis was explained by Pastor (1866), Vázquez Queipo (1866) or Guell and Ferrer (1869) and by economic historians such as Sánchez Albornoz (1962), Tortella (1973), Navas and Sudrià (2007), Tedde (2010) or Sudrià (2014). For the 1874 crisis see, Martínez y Gutiérrez (1874), Mansó y Gonzalez (1874) or Comín (2012).

⁹ We have considered 1874 as a debt crisis Martínez y Gutiérrez (1874), Mansó y González (1874), Comín (2012).

upsurge of most of these crises. Consequently, our empirical analysis is designed to contrast whether current account imbalances constitute a key determinant in Spanish financial crises. The main characteristics of Spanish crises are summarised in the following lines:

1850-1913: In the nineteenth century the frequency of financial crises in Spain was much higher than elsewhere in the world (with a frequency rate of 11.1 per cent for Spain, according to Betrán, Martín-Aceña and Pons 2012, and 4.9 per cent for the world average, following Bordo et al 2001) and crises were quite severe but less than the world average (with an output loss of 8 per cent for Spain and 9.8 per cent for the world, according to Bordo et al 2001). Key factors that singularized most nineteenth century financial crises in Spain included: railways and mining booms fueled by foreign capital entries¹⁰, with some eventual sudden stops, a banking expansion that increased credit growth, growing public budget deficits as well as current account imbalances. Moreover, some nineteenth century financial crises were also linked to a credit expansion in the years previous to the crisis (for example, in 1882). However, the impact of credit growth could be smoothed by the small size of the Spanish financial system: the ratio of Financial assets to GDP in Spain had an average of 0.2 between 1875-1900, whereas the average for 14 countries in the same period was around 0.7, more than triple the Spanish figure (Schularik and Taylor 2012).

1914-1936: there were four financial crises (1914, 1921, 1924 and 1931). With the exception of the 1931 crisis, the rest were not so severe. The low severity of these crises (with a zero output loss in 1921 and 1924) could be related to the neutrality of Spain during WWI and the huge positive trade balance that allowed paying debt, assets and bonds in foreign hands both, public and private (Sardá 1948, Sudrià 1990). As there is no data available for current account for the period 1914 to 1930, we have made a crude construction of the current account balance following Prados (2010)'s

¹⁰ As Prados (2010) remarks foreign capital played a non-negligible role in the nineteenth century by complementing domestic savings, especially in railways or mining. Using data from Moro, Nuño and Tedde (2015), the average ratio of Net Flows of Foreign Capital on total Gross Investment in Spain from 1856 to 1873 -the period with more accurate data for Spain- was around 32 per cent, clearly lower than in Argentina (70 per cent) or Mexico (75 per cent) for the period 1870-1910 but not so far from the rate in Canada (37 per cent) (O'Rourke and Williamson 2002).

methodology and considering Sudrià (1990)'s calculations (see Appendix 4 for data and procedures and Table 2 for the results). Our estimates show the net debtor position was extinguished and replaced by a net creditor position from 1914 to 1923 (Table 2). Furthermore, these crises had a low impact despite the fact that the 1921 and the 1924 crises were preceded by a rapid financial and credit expansion, especially from 1917 to 1922 when the real credit growth was around 19 per cent.

The deepest crisis in this period took place in 1931. The Great Depression was less severe in Spain than elsewhere in Europe, a perception already prevalent at that time¹¹, for several reasons. Firstly, the Bank of Spain behaved as a lender of last resort and, moreover, Spanish banks were loaded with gilt-edged securities and they pledged their unused portion of government paper to obtain cash (Martín-Aceña, Pons and Betrán 2014). Secondly, Spanish banks had no external indebtedness at that time. Finally, the strong depreciation of the *peseta* from 1927 to 1931 (-34.76 per cent and more than -50 per cent respect to the pound and the dollar respectively) (Eichengreen 1992).

Our estimates confirm that Spain did not face chronic current account imbalances during this period (Table 2). However, as in the 1920s, the 1931 crisis happened in a context of financial expansion, with annual average growth of real credit in the period 1929-31 of 9.43 per cent and an increase in the ratio of Financial Assets institutions to GDP from 0.91 in 1920 to 1.28 in 1929.

1940-2015: As in the rest of the world, from 1940 to 1972 the number of crises in Spain was low and without banking crises. The two crises of the 1940s (1943 and 1948) were not deep. The most severe was the 1958 crisis, with inflation and external imbalances.

Between 1973 and 2015 Spain suffered four financial crises. The most severe was that of 2008 (27.33 per cent) followed by 1976 (25.97 per cent) and 1982 crisis (23.62 per cent). In contrast with Bordo et al.'s (2001) results, post-1973 crises in Spain have not only been more frequent but

¹¹ See *Servicio de Estudios del Banco de España* (1934), Carreras and Tafunell (2003), Choudhri and Kochin (1980) and Temin (1993).

also more severe. External imbalances were behind all post-1973 crises (see Table 1 and Figure 1): 1976, 1982, 1991, 1995 and 2008. From the end of the 1950s Spain moved gradually to an open economy and there was a deterioration of the trade deficit that was easily covered by tourism revenues and migrant remittances (see Figure 1). However, after the oil crises (1973 and 1979), trade deficits could not be covered by them. Moreover, credit grew at high rates from the late 1960s in a financial system that expanded and changed from a ratio of Financial Assets to GDP of around 1.5 in 1968 to 2.12 in 1977. The crisis stemmed from the industrial to the banking sector through an increase in failed industrial firms and unpaid clients. The crisis was further aggravated by a stock market crash that deteriorated the balance sheets of those Spanish banks with large industrial portfolios (Cuervo 1988).

From the mid-1990s to 2007 Spain experienced a period of rapid growth (mainly based on the construction sector) that was sustained by foreign private debt and strong current account deficits (Betrán and Pons 2017). In 2008 the housing boom burst and banking institutions (saving banks involved in the construction sector) were damaged by the crisis and stopped lending. This change in the macroeconomic environment (and in particular the large increase in unemployment rates) had a direct impact on public finances producing a sovereign debt crisis. The international financial crisis restricted the access to international markets and produced a rise in default. In the 2008 crisis, therefore, there was an important increase in current account deficits the years before the crisis and also an important growth in real credit (see Table 1).

In short, in the study of the main drivers affecting Spanish financial crises in history, current imbalances seem to be behind the biggest crises in terms of output loss, such as in the nineteenth century crises, the 1976 recession and crises thereafter. Table 1 indicates that in the period with the highest severity (1973-2013), most of the crises were preceded by strong current account deficits, whereas in the period with the lowest severity (1914-1935), Spain did not have important current account difficulties. However, credit expansion was quite similar (9.43 per cent and 6.72 per cent

for the 1931 and the 1976 crises respectively). The lack of significance regarding credit expansion on financial crisis severity could be related to the relative backwardness and small size of the Spanish financial system during most of the period. Therefore, the current account imbalances hypothesis appears to be the most probable factor behind greater crisis severity until the most recent crisis.

3. Empirical findings: main estimations

In this section we estimate the relationship between crisis severity and current account deficits. We use the LP method proposed and developed by Jordà (2005) and Jordà, Schularick and Taylor (2013, 2016). The LP method is based on estimating separate regressions that are local to each forecast horizon and allow us to investigate the dynamic effect of financial crises on output. We have divided recession years into those with financial and with normal recessions, to account for the possibility that financial crises are endogenous to the business cycle, following Jordà, Schularick and Taylor (2013). As explained in Section 2, Spain has 19 financial recessions, whereas following Jordà, Schularick and Taylor (2011) who used the Bry and Boschan algorithm, we identify 14 normal recessions from 1850 to 2015¹². We have excluded the civil war years (1936-39). We will make use of data for Spain from 1850 to 2015 and we will consider all the years of the sample¹³ that consisted of recessions years and non-recessions years, as in the works of Rocha and Solomous (2015) or Teulings and Zubanov (2013).

¹² The normal recession years in Spain are: 1863, 1877, 1894, 1901, 1909, 1911, 1916, 1927, 1935, 1940, 1944, 1952, 1974, and 1980 (Berge and Jordà 2013).

¹³ As our analysis is only for a single country, we have considered the sample as large as possible to contemplate more observations and to have enough degrees of freedom, which is an important requirement for LP methods. For this reason, instead of making an estimate for a recession level sample (financial and normal recessions), we have added the non-recession years. However, we have also tested it with the short sample (financial and normal recessions) with 27 observations, because of the lack of data for some variables for the whole short sample (19 financial + 14 normal recessions). The results are maintained for all the regressions done in the paper.

We use LP methods to estimate the dynamic impact of financial crises on real output and to study how current account deficit impacts output from 1850 to 2015. Initially, we consider as the “treatment” variable *Excess Current Account* (the deviation of current account to GDP ratio with respect to its historical mean). Later on, we will also use the *Excess Credit* (the deviation of real credit growth with respect to its historical mean) as treatment variable to test the alternative hypothesis.

We show a summary of the statistics of the indicators and treatment variables (current account and credit) for financial recessions, normal recessions and non-recession periods in Appendix 6. We can observe that current account imbalances, measured by the current account to GDP ratio, in financial recessions, with a mean of -1.221, are greater than in normal recessions and non-recessions periods, with a mean respectively of -0.254 and -0.627. However, credit growth, measured by the three year lagged moving average of credit growth, is greater in financial recessions (with a mean of 4.5) than in normal recessions (with a mean of 2.9), but is not higher than in non-recession years (with a mean of 6.9).

The question we want to answer is whether current account imbalances influence the severity of financial crises in relation to normal recessions and non-recession years. We calculate the cumulative response of output at a horizon of h periods ($h=5$) in the future, in response to a “ β ” change in the treatment variable conditional on the lagged history of other control variables. Therefore, following Jordà, Schularick and Taylor (2013), we estimate separate regressions that are local to each forecast horizon and estimate the effect of a crisis event that occurs in year $t+h$, being $h=0$ at the year of the start of the crisis, on output in year $t+h$ ($h = 1, \dots, 5$) through the estimation of the following sequential equations:

$$\Delta y_{t+h} = \vartheta_F F + \vartheta_N N + \vartheta_{Non-R} Non-R + \beta_{h,F} F(\xi_t - \bar{\xi}_F) + \beta_{h,N} N(\xi_t - \bar{\xi}_N) + \beta_{h,Non-R} Non-R (\xi_t - \bar{\xi}_{Non-R}) + \sum_{l=0}^L \gamma_{t-l} \Gamma^l + u_t \quad [1]$$

where the dependent variable is the cumulative growth of GDP per capita in logs (“y”), that is, the log real GDP per capita (y) in years 1 through to 5 relative to its level in year 0, being year 0 the year of the financial crisis, the peak of the normal recession or the non-recession year.

We have differentiated among financial recessions (F), normal recessions (N) and non-recession years (Non-R) and the indicators of financial, normal recessions and non-recession years takes the value 1 when there is a year with one of these characteristics and 0 otherwise. ϑ_F is the common constant associated with financial recession treatment (F=1), ϑ_N is the common constant associated with normal recession treatment (N=1), and ϑ_{Non-R} is the common constant associated with periods of non-recession (Non-R=1). We have included several control variables (Υ_{t-l}) with l lags ($l = 2$), with coefficients Γ ; and u is the error term. The treatment variable ξ (in this case the ratio current account on GDP) enters in deviation from its mean in financial recessions, normal recessions and in periods of non-recession, respectively. The reason is that the mean can differ in these three periods. The coefficients $\beta_{h,F}$, $\beta_{h,N}$ and $\beta_{h,Non-R}$ measure the cumulated marginal effect of a unit treatment applied to ξ in each period (financial recession, normal recession and non-recession) on the path of the GDP per capita in a 5 year horizon.

We further take into account other factors that could have an effect on severity as a control. Firstly, we are interested in disentangling how robust the current account hypothesis is when we allow for the “credit” effect. Secondly, as explained in section 2, the narrative of the Spanish crises shows the importance of public imbalances in nineteenth century financial crises. We have finally controlled for investment/GDP as a proximate determinant of GDP growth. Therefore, the set of controls we have included are: a) real credit growth, b) fiscal or public budget on GDP and c) the investment on GDP ratio. As mentioned, the controls are 1-year and 2-year lagged values at horizon $h = 0$ ¹⁴.

¹⁴ We have presented the estimations with as few controls as possible to guarantee robust estimations given the small size of our sample; but when considering two more controls (the public debt to GDP ratio and the level of GDP per capita) we obtained similar results.

Table 3 displays the results estimated with the LP method of our hypothesis that current account imbalances are responsible for the higher severity of financial crises. We have included the treatment variable differentiated by its specific recession-type mean in financial recessions, normal recessions and the non-recession years¹⁵. We have also included the control variables and their coefficients are not shown. Our results indicate that financial recession path in relation to normal recession and non-recession path (F, N, Non-R) is significant in year 1, which means that the average financial crisis suffers a 2.8 per cent loss in the first year.

The coefficient associated to *excess current account* for the financial recession ranges between 0.735 and 2.710 and all of them are significant (from year 1 to year 5) and show that, for example, in the first three years the effect of a current account deficit produces around 2.1 per cent decrease in GDP per capita. The coefficients for a normal recession range from 0.555 to 1.428, but they are not significant. The coefficients for the non-recession periods are significant from year 2 to year 5. Table 3 includes the p-values of the F-test of equality of coefficients. The F-test for the horizons in years 2 to 5 indicate that the equality of coefficients of financial crises and non-recession years cannot be rejected for these horizons. To calculate the quantitative effect, given that the s.d. of the current account is 2.71, 2.44 and 2.47 respectively in financial, normal and non-recession years, in year 2, the cumulative marginal effects are higher in a financial recession than in a non-recession period. This implies that in the second year financial crises are more severe when there is a current account imbalance, all else being equal (1.417×2.71) in relation to normal recessions (0.772×2.44) and non-recession periods (0.607×2.47)¹⁶. Moreover, the results are robust when the 2008 crisis, the most severe crisis in Spanish history, is excluded from the sample.

¹⁵ We present the regressions with current account but we have also made the regressions with three year lagged moving average obtaining similar results.

¹⁶ To calculate the standardized coefficient we multiply the coefficient obtained in the regression by the standard deviation of the explanatory variable and divided by the standard deviation of the endogenous variable. In this case, for comparisons we do not need to divide by the standard deviation of the endogenous variable.

Figure 2 summarises the treatment responses using the coefficients obtained from Table 3. The figure displays the average treatment response path predicted when *excess current account* is perturbed in -1, -2, and -3 per cent per year above its mean in financial recessions, normal recessions and non-recession years¹⁷.

We have divided the sample in two subsamples for pre-1940 and post-1940 (see Appendix 7.1 and 7.2). For pre-1940, we obtained the significance of *excess current account* in financial recessions from year 1 to 4, excluding year 2, and in the non-recessions from year 3 to 5. In year 3 these two significant coefficients are different (as shown in the p-value of the test). For post-1940, all the coefficients in the financial recession are significant, as are those for a non-recession period since the second year. But we cannot reject that they are equal as we can notice with the results of the p-values in the F-test in Appendix 7.2.

We have also estimated by LP method considering *excess credit* by means of three year lagged moving average of real credit growth with respect to its means as a treatment control variable for financial and normal recessions, and non-recession periods. We contemplated in this case as control variables with the two lagged years: a) the current account to GDP ratio, b) the public budget to GDP ratio and c) the investment on GDP ratio. The results shown (Appendix 7.3) are for the full sample and exhibit that credit previous to a recession, financial and normal, is not significant, and conversely credit has a positive sign and contributed to cumulated per capita GDP growth in the non-recession period in year 1. However, in pre-1940, credit growth is not significant in the three treatments considered (F, N, Non-R). In post-1940, when the importance of credit was higher in the

¹⁷ As the treatment variable is *excess current account*, measured by current account balance on GDP, an *excess international borrowing* is perturbed in -1, -2 and -3 per cent per year, when there is a current account deficit. To calculate perturbations we have considered deviations in excess current account from average by amounts corresponding to -1/2.71, -2/2.44 and -3/2.47 standard deviations given that the standard deviation of current account is 2.71, 2.44 and 2.47 in financial and normal recessions and non-recession years (see Appendix 6).

Spanish economy, credit was significant from year 1 to 2 in non-recession years but it did not have a significant effect in a financial recession period¹⁸.

Finally, we have also followed another methodological approach inspired by Jordà, Schularick and Taylor (2016) that tried to address potential reverse causality. Given that *excess current account* could predict a crisis, we want to avoid any problem of endogeneity. As a consequence, we have also estimated LP using inverse propensity-score weighting regression adjustment (IPWRA). The propensity score model is also estimated over the sample for all years (financial and normal recessions, and non-recessions) where we predict, using a multinomial logit model, financial versus normal recessions and non-recessions, considering two lags of this set of controls. We are again interested in the cumulative change in log real GDP per capita “y” from today ($h=0$) to some future period h ($h = 1, 2, \dots, 5$) and we consider financial recessions (F), normal recessions (N) and non-recessions (Non-R) that take the “unordered” categorical value of $F=1$, $N=2$ and $\text{Non-R}=3$. In a first stage, using a multinomial logit, we estimate the probability that the recession constitutes a financial crisis against normal recessions and non-recessions. We have treated financial crisis (F) as the base. The second stage consists of estimating previous specification [1] using weighted least-squared (WLS) using the probability “ \hat{p} ” estimated, the estimated probability that the recession constitutes a financial crisis, and the associated weights $\omega = F/\hat{p} + N/(1 - \hat{p}) + \text{Non-R}/(1 - \hat{p})$, that is, using inverse probability weighted regression adjusted (IPWRA), which implies a doubly robust estimate (given observable controls). Weighting by the inverse of the propensity score allows us to put more weight on those observations that are more difficult to predict because they are closest to random allocation. Moreover, we estimated the propensity score using a multinomial logit model across the separate pre-1940 and post-1940 samples.

¹⁸ We obtain similar results when considering the change in the Credit to GDP ratio (three-year moving average).

Table 4 displays IPWRA estimates with robust standard errors. As in the case of previous LP method, we obtain that financial recession path is only significant in the first year but now with a deeper impact (-3.484 per cent in contrast to the previous -2.782 per cent). The results show differences between financial and normal recessions and non-recession years. Both financial and normal recessions display positive and significant correlations between *excess current account* and output per capita in the five years (with the exception of year 3 in normal recessions). In the case of a non-recession year, the coefficients are positive and significant from year 2 to 5. We provide a test of the null that, at each horizon, the coefficients are statistically equal to each other. The F-test of equality of coefficients between financial and normal recessions indicates that we cannot reject the null hypotheses of equality from year 1 to 2 and are not equal in years 3, 4 and 5. This means that current account imbalances have the same effect in financial and normal recessions for the two first years and different for the last three years. However, the F-test of equality of the coefficients between financial recessions and non-recessions suggest that they are not equal from years 1 to 4, when both variables are significant, with p-values of 6 per cent, 8 per cent, 0 per cent and 7 per cent respectively. In year 2 given that the s.d. of the current account is 2.71, 2.44 and 2.47 for financial recessions, normal recessions and non-recessions respectively, these coefficients imply that a +1 s.d. change in *excess current account* deficit would decrease output in $(1.333*2.71)$ for a financial recession, $(0.743*2.44)$ for a normal recession, and $(0.596*2.47)$ for a non-recession period. This means that the impact of excess international borrowing is higher in a financial recession than in a normal recession and non-recession year, and higher in a normal recession than in a non-recession year. As happens previously, these results are also robust when the 2008 crisis is excluded from the sample.

We also present as before, the IPWRA estimations for pre-1940 and post-1940 (Appendix 7.4 and 7.5). In the first subsample, we obtain that *excess current account* is significant at the horizon year 1, 3, 4 and 5 in a financial recession and significant in a normal recession at 5 year horizons.

Notwithstanding, it is significant in a non-recession period in the years 3, 4 and 5. The F-test of equality of coefficients has a p-value of 1 per cent in year 3, thus *excess current account* in a financial recession has a different impact in relation to a normal recession and a non-recession year. However, from year 4 to 5, it has an equal impact because we cannot reject the null that the coefficients are statistically equal to each other. The results show that the impact of a 1 per cent increase of s.d. at horizon 3 is more than around 2 and 3 times respectively higher on average in a financial recession than in a normal recession and a non-recession ($3.325*1.84$, $1.328* 2.57$ and $0.879*2.34$ correspondingly) and at horizon 4 and 5 there are no differences.

For the post-1940, *excess current account* is not significant during a normal recession (Appendix 7.5). However, the coefficients of *excess current account* during a financial recession are statistically significant at each horizon of five years. The coefficients in non-recession years are significant from year 2 to 5, but we cannot reject the null of equality of the coefficients between the financial recession and non-recession period in years 3 and 4. If we compare the effect of current account deficits in pre-1940 and post 1940, given an increase of 1 per cent of s.d. of current account imbalance on the GDP per capita growth in year 3, we obtain a reduction of 0.822 ($(3.325*1.84)/7.44$) in the first period, versus a reduction of 0.895($(2.017*3.23)/7.28$) in the second period.

As shown in Section 2, in the nineteenth century and the beginning of the twentieth century, current account deficits mainly reflected high capital entries due to a low level of national savings relative to investment. However, in the post-1940 period current account deficits were the result of trade deficits accumulated after economic growth that highlighted the structural problems and lack of competitiveness of the Spanish economy. The regressions for the two sub-samples allow us to test the different impact.

As we can see above¹⁹ the standardised coefficients associated to current account imbalances in financial recessions are slightly lower in pre-1940 than in post-1940. This means that a +1 s.d change in current account has a lower impact on output in pre-1940. Moreover, as the magnitude of the current account deficits was greater in post-1940 (with a mean of -0.038 in contrast to -4.442 in the respective periods, as shown in Table 5), in the end the quantitative impact of current account imbalances on financial recessions was higher in post-1940.

In conclusion LP methods, and specially IPWRA corrected for a possibility of endogeneity, determine that, all else being equal, current account imbalances are associated with deeper financial crises. Therefore, the narrative of Spanish crises and estimations alike suggest that current account deficits could explain higher output losses and lower economic growth. By contrast, real credit growth is not associated with more severe financial recessions.

6. Conclusions

From the study of the 19 financial crises that have occurred in Spain over the last 165 years, we document a different pattern in terms of severity than in international crises. Post-1973 crises were more severe, with an impact that was around double that of the world average. However interwar crises, including the 1930 depression had an impact that was a third lower than the world average.

We record the main drivers behind Spanish financial crises severity over the last 165 years, where current account imbalances provide the most common warning. We estimate the relationship between the main hypothesis and crisis intensity by using LP methods that allow us to estimate the dynamic impact of financial crises on real output. As we had no current account data for the interwar years, we have estimated them for the period 1914-1930. We have considered all types of financial crises (banking, currency, stock market and debt), which should enrich the analysis by considering

¹⁹ See the Appendix 5.6 and 5.7 where the regression is broken down into pre- and post-1940.

important crises in Spanish financial history. We found that current account imbalances in periods of financial crisis have a significant and higher impact than the current account in periods of normal recession and non-recession. The alternative hypothesis of leverage has not been so decisive or has been channelled through foreign capital and current account imbalances as a source of financial instability.

There seems to be a clear relationship between economic expansion linked to the modernization and industrialisation of the Spanish economy and high current account deficits. Prados (2010) obtains that from 1850 to 1890 the current account deficit allowed the rate of investment and stimulated economic growth to increase. In the twentieth century we also observe periods of high growth that were associated with current account deficits. In this sense, it is not clear that in the long term the external sector has acted as a restriction to Spain's economic growth. However, our results indicate that the external position has increased vulnerability and financial instability by producing more severe crises.

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The relevant material related to all appendices is available in the online appendix.

Table 1: Duration and Depth of Crises in Spain, by year and type of crisis

Crisis year	Type of crisis	Duration (years)	Depth (%)	Crisis with current account/ GDP deficit (**) (%)	Crisis with real credit growth (**) (%)
1855	Stock Market + D	3	-5.62		n.d
1866	Twin 2 (B+SM) +D	3	-11.28	-3.68	5.14
1874	Stock Market + D	1	-10.58	-0.99	
1882	Triple (C+B+SM) + D	6	-13.52		35.76
1892(*)	Triple (C+B+SM)	5	-11.77		9.58
1899	Currency + D	1	-0.25		2.52
1905	Stock Market	1	-3.24	-0.33	
1850-1913		2.83	-8.04	-0.30	4.64
1914	Twin 2 (B+SM)	2	-3.46		
1921	Triple (C+B+SM)	1	0		16.79
1924	Banking	1	0	-2.13	11.82
1931	Triple (C+B+SM)	3	-13.04	-1.30	9.43
1919-1935		1.75	-4.12	-0.42	12.68
1943	Currency	1	0		n.d
1948	Twin 3 (C+SM)	3	-7.97		n.d
1958	Twin 3 (C+SM)+D	3	-9.57	-1.99	2.86
1945-1972		2.33	-5.85	-1.06	2.86
1976	Triple (C+B+SM)+D	6	-25.97	-3.89	6.72
1982	Twin 1 (C+B)	5	-23.62	-2.53	4.99
1991	Twin 3 (C+SM)	4	-6.25	-3.16	7.44
1995	Currency	2	-1.48	-0.65	
2008	Twin 1 (C + B) + D	6	-27.33	-9.22	15.48
1973-2015		4.6	-16.93	-2.56	6.53

Note: C: Currency, B: Banking, SM: Stock Market, D: Debt, Twin 1 is a combination of currency and banking crises. Twin 2 is a combination of banking and stock market crises. Twin 3 is a combination of currency and stock market crises. Triple is a combination of currency, banking and stock market crises. (*) 1892 stock market crisis and 1890 banking crisis. Depth or GDP loss and duration definition see text. (**) Three year lagged moving average.

Source: Betrán, Martín Aceña and Pons (2012), Betrán and Pons (2017), Comín (2012), Martínez and Nogués (2014) and Reinhart and Rogoff (2010).

Table 2: Trade and Current Account balance and External Indebtedness, 1914-1934

	Trade balance (Million pesetas)	Ratio Trade Balance/GDP (%)	Current account Balance (Million pesetas)	Ratio Current Account balance/GDP (%)	External indebtedness (Million pesetas)
1914	11	0.08	499	3.77	-1,793
1915	315	2.14	826	5.61	-2,316
1916	49	0.29	651	3.83	-1,827
1917	656	3.53	1363	7.35	-1,110
1918	289	1.28	1080	4.77	-24
1919	1,020	4.21	1761	7.27	-2,057
1920	-1,332	-4.67	-198	-0.69	-1,517
1921	-741	-2.85	27	0.11	-1,433
1922	-1,194	-4.42	-425	-1.61	-916
1923	-1,652	-6.27	-844	-3.21	-73
1924	-1,396	-4.87	-533	-1.86	474
1925	-1,055	-3.45	-162	-0.53	635
1926	-395	-1.33	499	1.68	197
1927	-761	-2.84	127	0.40	288
1928	-1,108	-3.58	-422	-1.36	767
1929	-1,255	-3.74	-595	-1.77	1,395
1930	-981	-2.90	-250	-0.74	1,076
1931	-514	-1.55	-516	-1.55	1,340
1932	-646	-1.95	-82	-0.25	1,632
1933	-447	-1.41	-105	-0.33	2,103
1934	164	0.47	531	1.52	3,319

Source: Current Account balance from 1914 to 1930 own estimates (see Appendix 2 for data and procedures).

Table 3: Local projections: Real GDP per capita in financial recessions versus normal recessions and non-recession years with Excess Current Account as a treatment variable, 1850-2015

Deviation of Log of real GDP per capita (relative to year 0, $\times 100$) Sample: All years	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Financial recession	-2.782*	-2.447	-3.913	-3.630	-5.388
	(1.469)	(2.229)	(2.685)	(3.140)	(3.548)
Normal recession	1.113	-1.597	-2.988	-2.804	-1.902
	(1.387)	(2.105)	(2.536)	(2.965)	(3.350)
Non-recession years	-1.136	-0.563	-0.298	-0.112	-0.128
	(1.059)	(1.606)	(1.935)	(2.263)	(2.557)
Excess Current Account \times Financial recession	0.735*	1.417**	2.111***	2.454***	2.710***
	(0.380)	(0.576)	(0.695)	(0.812)	(0.918)
Excess Current Account \times Normal recession	0.557	0.723	0.772	1.015	1.428
	(0.504)	(0.765)	(0.921)	(1.077)	(1.217)
Excess Current Account \times Non-recession years	0.219	0.607**	1.203***	1.800***	2.227***
	(0.183)	(0.278)	(0.335)	(0.391)	(0.442)
F-test equality of coefficients:					
Financial = Normal (p)	0.02	0.73	0.75	0.81	0.37
Financial = Non-recession (p)	0.14	0.26	0.08	0.14	0.05
Excess Current Account, Financial = Normal (p)	0.77	0.45	0.23	0.26	0.38
Excess Current Account, Financial = Non-recession (p)	0.19	0.17	0.21	0.43	0.61
Observations	129	129	129	129	129
R-squared	0.219	0.487	0.583	0.634	0.671

Note: Dependent variable $\Delta_h y_{t+h}$ = change in log real GDP per capita from year 0 to year $h \times 100$. Full sample: 1850-2015. Spanish Civil War is excluded (1936-1939). Robust Standard errors in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. Control variables and WWI dummy coefficients are not shown. WWII dummy is not necessary given that this period has been excluded because lack of credit data for this period. For each F-test of equality of coefficients are reported the p-values of the test. For the variable definition see text.

Table 4: Local projections: Real GDP per capita in financial recessions versus normal recessions and non-recession years using inverse propensity-score weighting adjustment (IPWRA) with Excess Current Account as a treatment variable, 1850-2015

Log of real GDP per capita (relative to year 0, $\times 100$)	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Sample: All years	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Financial recession	-3.484** (1.731)	-3.161 (2.499)	-3.156 (2.559)	-2.698 (3.060)	-3.113 (3.712)
Normal recession	0.833 (1.324)	-2.142 (1.754)	-3.347 (2.808)	-3.093 (2.440)	-1.921 (2.523)
Non-recession years	-1.330 (1.217)	-0.933 (1.905)	-0.400 (1.995)	-0.0456 (2.354)	0.338 (2.425)
Excess Current Account \times Financial recession	0.574*** (0.191)	1.333*** (0.421)	2.189*** (0.354)	2.603*** (0.424)	3.078*** (0.693)
Excess Current Account \times Normal recession	0.576* (0.343)	0.743* (0.433)	0.803 (0.622)	1.010* (0.571)	1.359** (0.658)
Excess Current Account \times Non-recession years	0.207 (0.197)	0.596** (0.284)	1.223*** (0.327)	1.819*** (0.417)	2.248*** (0.463)
F-test equality of coefficients:					
Financial = Normal (p)	0.01	0.62	0.94	0.89	0.74
Financial = Non-recession (p)	0.06	0.14	0.09	0.21	0.26
Excess Current Account, Financial = Normal (p)	1.00	0.30	0.03	0.01	0.06
Excess Current Account, Financial = Non-recession (p)	0.06	0.08	0.00	0.07	0.23
Observations	129	129	129	129	129
R-squared	0.419	0.490	0.583	0.631	0.675

Note: Dependent variable $\Delta_h y_{t+h}$ = change in log real GDP per capita from year 0 to year $h \times 100$. Full sample: 1850-2013. Spanish Civil War is excluded (1936-1939). Robust Standard errors in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. Control variables and WWI dummy coefficients are not shown. WWII dummy is not necessary given that this period has been excluded because lack of credit data for this period. For each F-test of equality of coefficients are reported the p-values of the test. The variables are weighted by the inverse propensity score for the probability of observing financial crisis recession instead of normal recession and non-crisis period. For the variable definition see text.

Source: See Data Appendix.

Note: See text. Solid lines show predicted paths from Table 5 considering the coefficients and the mean of all variables including controls and IWW dummy, dashed lines show paths when excess international borrowing is perturbed in -1, -2, and -3 per cent per year in Financial recessions, Normal recessions and Non-recession years.